

SOCIAL CAPITAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL CAPITAL OF B.ED STUDENT TEACHERS

A. H. Komala* & Dr. S. Vasanthi**

* Research Scholar, N.K.T National College of Education for Women,
Chennai, Tamilnadu

** Principal, N.K.T National College of Education for Women, Chennai, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

Recent technological advancements have reduced the face to face interactions among the people therefore resulting in poor quality of life. In order to have a better quality of Life it is essential to boost the Psychological and Social Aspects of Student-Teachers. The aim of the present investigation is to find out the relationship between Psychological Capital and Social Capital of B.Ed. Student-Teachers. The investigation tends to explore the relationship between the two variables taken for the present study. 200 B.Ed. Student-Teachers representing Government, Government-aided and Self-financing institutions were chosen as samples for the present study. The collected data were statistically processed finding Correlation, t- test and F-test. It is proved that there is significant relationship between the two variables and significant differences were found gender wise and based on number of friends.

Key Words: Psychological Capital, Social Capital, and Student-Teachers.

Introduction:

Transition is common in all human endeavors. Students today are tech savvy, and largely depend on technology related gadgets or devices for all activities right from Education to Recreation. Technology is so dominant and has its own favorable and adverse effects. This Technology Era has resulted in poor social skill. In fact children of today are not only socially backward and deprived also lost in the ICT related Technology World. As the Children of today are distancing themselves from human touch they are bundled with stress. This quality of not venting out their feelings and emotions in right dose and at right time has resulted in making the individuals timid and psychologically unfit to encounter the realistic issues that they come across during their life time. Student-Teachers in the present condition are added to more technological up gradation which has ultimately resulted in poor social capital. The term stress and depression has become common word irrespective of to which age group does the student-teacher fall. The Student –Teachers of today are also psychologically unfit to face and overcome realistic situation. Therefore their psychological capital is also poorly developed in them.

Psychological Capital:

Three capitals occupy a pivotal position they are psychological capital, human capital and social capital. Psychological capital though started in organizational set up it has spread its hands through out in all dimensions. Psychological capital focuses on self and possible self. Psychological capital will help healthy people to contribute to the development of the society. The concept of helping healthy people thereby adds on to the output and improving human potential. Developing positive psychological capital will help oneself to go beyond the expectation and turn successful by facing all realistic situations.

Characteristics of Psychological Capital:

Psychologically healthy person are tend to possess these traits. To become committed and taking effort for success in challenging affairs and tasks (self-efficiency), positive citation for present and future achievements (optimism), the stability in achieving the objective and changing the way to goal to achieve the success (hope) if necessary, the perseverance while facing with difficulties and problems to achieve the success (resiliency).

Definitions:

"Psychological capital can be defined as a complement of personal and organizational features which can be developed and directed" Luthans F. Psychological capital consists of hope, optimism, self-efficacy, resilience which is essential for success, to remain motivated in a task, with perseverance. (Luthans, Avolio, Avey, & Norman, 2007).

Social Capital:

Social Capital is well thought-out multidimensional and cannot permanently be viewed as a single component, but relatively requires deliberation from multiple dimensions, levels, forms, types and other interrelated elements. Over the years, a number of attempts have been made to measure an individual's networks and associated resources in the form of strength of relationships, density of relationships, usefulness of relationships, types of resources, and availability of resources. Social capital exists in the form of resources that can be utilized in the accomplishment of expressive actions to maintain well-being, such as in the form of functional support and emotional backing.

Social Capital must be viewed in two perspectives: one from the capacity to procure information, ideas and support of others as a result of maintaining the relationship with other people as supported by sociologist Ronald Burt, Nan Lin, and Alejandro Portes's accessible due to improved relationship. According to Robert Putnam Social Capital is on account of individual's involvement in informal network and formal social network which may help them to solve a number of social problems and thus contribute towards civic health. The third view called linking social Capital (Woolcock 1999, World Bank 2000) can help to link and bridge and contribute to development of individuals both horizontally and vertically.

Definitions:

The definition from the Office for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) is "networks together with shared norms, values and understandings that facilitate co-operation within or among groups". Social Capital Theory of James Coleman (1990) defines social capital as a function of social structure producing advantage. Various entities consist of some aspects of social structure; and which facilitates certain actions of individuals who are within the structure.

Literature Review:

The importance of social capital in supporting students from low socio economic backgrounds and from families that have no higher education family tradition is becoming increasingly apparent. Social capital requires co-operation, trust, reciprocity, civic engagement and collective well-being. Putnam (1993) drew this conclusion from a longitudinal study conducted in Italy over 20 years from 1970. These elements of social capital are often used to explore the strength of a given community.

Melissa, Julia and Takuya (2018) examined differences in social capital between two demographically disparate groups: future education professionals and youth leaders living in urban communities. This is important because there is growing scholarly evidence of a positive relationship between social capital and student achievement. "Social capital," defined as a constellation of privileges, is parallel to "the concepts of financial capital, physical capital, and human capital--but embodied in relations among persons" (Coleman, 1988). The impact of the varying access to social capital and its attendant resources may have profound implications on the interactions within the classroom; thus, this study measured this construct in a sample of students in education preparation programs (n = 145) and a sample of youth leaders living in urban communities (n = 119). There were significant differences between groups in: community participation, value of life, and feelings of trust and safety. Educational and consultative strategies to develop cultural competence and diversity sensitivity are discussed, with a particular focus on training future school professionals.

Ngoma and Peter (2016) investigated the relationship among Psychological Capital, career identity, employability of the graduates with the mediating role of Social Capital in Uganda. From the population of 480 unemployed people undergoing skill development programme 215 respondent was chosen. Regression, Differential analysis was adopted in processing the data collected. It was found that nearly 15 percent of variations, in the employability, of the samples were accounted for the variables Psychological capital, Social Capital, and career identity. Social Capital is found to completely mediate between the other variables of the study. It was suggested to improve on the employees Psychological Capital, social capital and work identity to be successful in employment.

Qiangwei, Yan (2016) explored coping style on interpersonal relationship treating Psychological Capital as mediating variable. 832 college students from Wuhan City were selected. Cluster sampling technique was adopted in this study. Psychological Capital Questionnaire (PCQ) and the Simplified Coping Style Questionnaire (SCSQ) were used. Significant influence was found between the dependent and independent variable.

Moschetti and Hudley (2015) administered a grounded theory approach to study the academic and social adjustment of first-generation, low-income White students. This study verified the research situation with the theoretical notion of being provided with adequate social support, assistance to facilitate first generation degree learners. It was found that better social capital provided the students with better information, guidance and emotional support. It was suggested to provide better social capital to help the white learners to overcome obstacles to reach their academic goals.

Hansen, Buitendach and Kanengoni (2014) examined the relationship between Psychological Capital (Psychological Capital), subjective well-being, burnout and job satisfaction of South African Educators. The study found that by means of enhancing the subjective well-being of teachers is found not only to improve their performance and commitment, but at large it is found to have an impact on the satisfaction of students. The cross-sectional method was adopted. 103 teacher educators served as sample for this study. Psychological Capital was found to reconcile between subjective well-being and burnout. The researcher also suggested, in improving on the components of subjective well-being, and job satisfaction when they are in distress.

Barmola (2013) studied the Psychological Capital of 100 adolescent student's public school in Jaipur. The investigator attempted to study the gender difference in all the four components of Psychological Capital namely Self Efficacy, Hope, Resilience, and optimism. Gender difference was found only in the component of hope and there was no difference in all the other three components of Psychological Capital.

Luthans et al. (2007) conducted two studies on the dimensions of Psychological Capital as predictor of performance and satisfaction both the studies found the four dimensions to be indicator of performance and also concluded that composite dimension to be better predictor of performance than the individual dimensions.

Objectives of the Study:

The objectives of the present study are:

- To investigate the relationship between Psychological capital and Social Capital of B.Ed. Student-teachers.
- To explore the Gender difference in the variables namely Psychological Capital and Social Capital.
- To explore the difference in the variables namely Psychological Capital and Social Capital with respect to Number of friends

Hypotheses of the Study:

Based the objectives the following hypotheses were framed

- There exists significant relationship between Psychological Capital and Social Capital of B.Ed. Student- teachers.
- There exists no significant gender difference in the Psychological Capital and Social Capital of B.Ed. Student- teachers.
- There exists no significant difference in Psychological Capital and Social Capital of B.Ed. Student-teachers with respect to number of friends.

Method of the Study:

Normative survey method has been adopted to collect sample for the present study.

Samples for the Study:

The Present study is intended to explore the Psychological Capital and Social Capital of B.Ed. Student-teacher. The Student-Teachers in Chennai city were selected to be sample from three types of Management namely Government –aided, and Self- financing Institution. Around 200 samples were collected from student- teachers.

Tools for the Study:

The tools that were originally prepared by the authors were adapted for the purpose of present with the aim to suit to the present environmental background and culture of the samples groups.

- Psychological Capital Scale - Adapted Psychological Capital modified the following tools of Luthans, Luthans, & Jensen, 2012, Michael F. Scheier & Charles S. Carver. (1985). The Herth Hope Index (Hhi) 1992, Siriporn Sapyaprapa, ArunyaTuicomepee, Rewadee Watakakosol, 2013.Modified and validated by A. H. Komala and Dr. S. Vasanthi
- Social Capital Scale - Adapted Classroom Social Capital Scale-Revised (CSCS-R) Student Form developed by May Belle N. Trahan 2013. Modified and Validated by A. H. Komala’s and Dr. S. Vasanthi

Statistical Technique Used:

The collected data was tabulated and statistically processed and the results are interpreted based on the tables present below.

Table 1: Correlation between Psychological Capital and Social Capital scores of Student-Teachers

Variables	Psychological Capital	Social Capital
Psychological Capital	1	0.683**
Social Capital	0.683**	1

The above table is clearly indicating that there exist significant relationship between the two variables chosen for the present study namely Psychological Capital and Social Capital which is mutually contributing to one another. The theoretical background collected stated that Student-Teachers who are strong in their Social Capital are found to have strong Psychological Capital and inversely Student-Teachers who are psychologically well balanced can move with others calmly without any complexities. Both the variables are positively correlated indicating that increase in the contribution one will have a direct increase in the contribution of the other variable. The result drawn is significant at 0.01 level thus accepting the hypothesis framed.

Table 2:Gender wise difference in Psychological Capital and Social Capital of B.Ed. Student-Teachers

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t- value	Level of Significance
Psychological Capital	Boys	100	61.03	5.060	0.000**
	Girls	100	63.74		
Social Capital	Boys	100	57.22	5.893	0.000**
	Girls	100	60.10		

It could be inferred from the table that there exists significant gender difference in the Student-Teachers in their Psychological Capital and Social Capital. Both the boys and girls student-teachers are found to be significantly different in their Psychological Capital and Social Capital.

Though boys and Girls in our system are given equal opportunity in all fields there still exist significant differences. Further it is evident from the mean value that girls are found to have better Psychological Capital of 63.74 than boys with 61.03. Basically girls can handle critical situation in a balanced ways can be due Indian Set-up, as they shoulder more roles and responsibility both at home, place of study or at work place.

Similarly there existed significant difference in the Social capital between Boys and Girls. Socially building ones skill is highly essential in our technologically driven society. Girls are found to have better social skill than boys which is well depicted by mean value. As mention above the social capital is the ability to move with newer people. Girls due to their predominant roles played in their society face more individuals. Mean value of 60.10 is greater than 57.22 indicating the ability of girls to mingle and develop better social skill.

Table 3: One Way ANOVA results of Psychological Capital and Social Capital of B.Ed. Student-Teachers based on number of Friends

Variables	df	Mean Square	F	Significance	Groups Differ Significantly
Psychological Capital	5	259.305	1.220	NS	-
	195	212.506			
Social Capital	5	208.082	2.051	0.039	(3&4), (3&1), (3&5), (2&4), (2&1), (2&5),
	195	101.475			

The One way Analysis carried on establishing the Psychological and Social Capital of B.Ed. Student-Teachers make it evident that there is no difference in the Psychological Capital of the samples based on number of Friends as the p-value is greater than 0.05 indicating that the 200 samples of B.Ed. Student-Teachers are found to have the same level of Psychological Capital irrespective of number of Friends thus accepting the null hypothesis.

Further on analyzing the p-value for Social Capital for the chosen 200 samples it was found to have significant difference thus rejecting the null hypothesis. On administering the post-hoc test the Duncan directional table indicate that there exists significant difference between the groups with 3 friends with that having 1,4,5 friends similarly, difference is found between the group of 2 friends with 1,4,5 friends. This directional table leads to inference that more the number of friends the better their Social Capital. Thus rejecting the null hypothesis and accepting the alternative hypothesis.

Findings of the Study:

- The Psychological capital and Social Capital of B.Ed. Student-Teachers are positively correlated.
- There is gender difference in Psychological capital and Social Capital of B.Ed. Student-teachers. Thus rejecting null hypothesis formed and accepting alternative hypothesis. In both the variables girls were found to be better than boys.
- There is no significant difference in Psychological Capital based on number of Friends indicating how many ever friends we have Psychological Capital remains the same.
- There is significant difference in Social Capital based on number of Friends indicating higher the number of friends better the Social Capital and Vice-versa, thus rejecting the null hypothesis.

Implications:

Prospective Student-Teachers are the makers of Nation tomorrow thus highlighting the need for well-developed Teachers for better tomorrow. It is indicated that both Psychological Capital and Social Capital are related thus it is the bound duty of Educational Institutions at all levels right from Schooling to The Higher Education or Professional courses to incorporate value-added or Add-on courses to build in the Students both Psychological and Social Capital and thereby equipping the Prospective Student-Teachers to contribute to the development of good citizens for our Country. Right from day one of any student entering School to get educated must be developed holistically and not only on academics.

Conclusion

This present study has clearly thrown light on the need for a student-teacher to be equipped in their Psychological and Social Capitals domains as they are the one who prepare the future citizens of our Nation. Taking this into consideration it is duty of our Educational System to equip students on all aspects so as to develop them holistically. In order to maintain oneself in social order it is essential to be emotionally well balanced. Psychological capital is hypothesized to empower students with the necessary mental strength to cope up with adverse circumstances. Luthans, Avolio et al. (2007), suggest that strategies can be developed to better shape these dispositions among young adults and facilitate their coping with stress exposures. As that of Social Capital is concerned conscious effort is required to reintroduce students to those worlds of joy that can be gathered from real-world caring connotation. To develop both the capitals it is necessary to bring the individuals in touch with the society.

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